

BEHAVIORAL TENDENCIES OF INTERMEDIATE PUPILS AT INDANAN SOUTH DISTRICT ELEMENTARY SCHOOL AT MINISTRY OF BASIC, HIGHER AND TECHNICAL EDUCATION IN SULU: TEACHER'S PERSPECTIVE

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ABSTRACT

This study is descriptive-qualitative research determining the extent of behavioral tendencies of intermediate pupils at Indanan south district elementary school MBHTE-Sulu: Teachers' perspective. Employing weighted mean, standard deviation, t-test for independent samples, one-way ANOVA, and Pearson's r test of correlation. The following are the findings of this study: 1) Out of 100 teacher-respondents, great majority are within 31 years old and above of age brackets, are female and most are married and with bachelor's degree. 2) Sub-categories subsumed under the extent of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District elementary school as perceived by the teachers in the context of Activity Level, Emotional control and aggression and destructiveness is all rated as "less extent" with total weighted mean score of 3.12, 2.73, 2.01 with standard deviation of 1.04310, 1.03469, 1.352 respectively by the teacher-respondents at Indanan South District Elementary School involved in this study. 3) Generally, there is no significant difference in the extent of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District elementary school as perceived by teachers when data are grouped according to their educational attainment and civil status. However, teacher-respondents perceived differently on the extent of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District elementary school when data are grouped according to their age and gender. 4) Generally the sub-categories subsumed under the extent of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District elementary school as perceived by the teachers are highly correlated. Moreso, this study recommends the following: 1) DepEd administrators should ensure access to support services such as counseling, special education, and health and nutrition programs to address the diverse needs of intermediate pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School and promote their holistic development. 2) Teachers at the Indanan South district Elementary School may prioritize their own professional development and growth to stay abreast of current research, best practices, and

emerging trends in education. Engaging in ongoing training, workshops, and professional learning sessions focusing on behavior management strategies. 3) Educators are encouraged to adopt a holistic approach to behavior assessment, considering multiple dimensions such as social, emotional, and academic behaviors. Implement frameworks or tools that facilitate comprehensive behavior assessment, allowing educators to capture the interconnected nature of student behavior more accurately, and, 4) More so, Future researchers in the field of Education are encouraged to conduct study like this one to further assess the behavioral tendency of intermediate pupils and how will this impact their academic performance, socio-emotional development, and overall well-being.

Keywords: *Behavioral Tendencies, Teachers' Perspective, MBHTE, Descriptive Research.*

INTRODUCTION

Seeing students' inclinations in terms of behavior is crucial for teachers to do since teaching is more than just directing students' learning and passing along information. Rather, as a process, it ensures students' emotional, spiritual, cognitive, and social well-being in addition to their behavior's consistency. It also focuses on addressing potential behavioral tendencies in students that could have a negative effect on their education and interpersonal interactions. Furthermore, considering our combined experiences as parents and educators, we believe that teachers should look into behavioral issues with their pupils because the longer they remain untreated, the worse they get.

Two related clusters of problematic behaviors were found by Algozzine (2017), and they are extremely pertinent to the educational environment. One grouping, known as the social defiance cluster, included lazy and uncooperative behavior in addition to violent and destructive disobedient actions. On the other hand, motor behavior was perceived considerably differently, as it was thought to be determined naturally. The cluster of social immaturity encompassed depressive and nervous behaviors, inactivity, as well as clumsiness and nonsensical speaking.

The "striving" for objects that hinder or enable goal- or need-directed behavior is the fundamental cause of the tendency (see, for example, Frijda, 1986, 2010; Cacioppo et al., 2000; Kreibig et al., 2010). There has been an attempt to reconcile the discrete action program and motivation-grounded viewpoints on action inclination and emotional action. Christie and Friedman (2004) found that the "basic" emotions—anger, fear, sadness, amusement, contentment, and disgust—mapped onto the continuous dimensions 4. According to Ekman (2003) and Levenson et al. (2011), the fundamental emotions are: fear, happiness, disgust, rage, sadness, and surprise.

Other social and emotional difficulties, including as sadness, suicide, and impairments, have also been linked to behavioral problems among students [1–2]. Additionally, these issues have a severe effect on kids' social and psychological growth, which could have an adverse effect on their capacity for constructive interpersonal connection as well as their learning and academic success. In this way, behavioral

problems may prevent students from learning in the classroom during their formative years, which may prevent them from acquiring the skills necessary to succeed as adults and professionals in a distant setting in the future. Our experience has shown that in order to create learning environments that support both general and tailored learning experiences, a methodical planning, implementation, and monitoring approach is needed, one that addresses both behavioral difficulties and learning impediments.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The entire plan or approach utilized to carry out a research study, including the techniques for gathering and analyzing data, is referred to as the research design. A research design aids in guaranteeing that the study is carried out methodically and rigorously and that the findings are legitimate and dependable. (Thomson, N., Proulx, M., & Lindsay, S. 2017).

The descriptive-qualitative research methodology was applied in this study. A fact-finding study using a descriptive research method entails a thorough and accurate interpretation of the findings in order to characterize a particular current situation.

By employing the descriptive technique, the researcher hopes to investigate and explore the reasons of a specific condition as well as characterize the characteristics of the condition that existed during the study period. In order to create a logical and cogent conclusion and suggestions for the study, the researcher decided to employ this kind of research methodology, taking into account the goal to obtain first-hand information from the respondents. The purpose of descriptive method research was to collect data regarding the current state of affairs, according to Creswell (1994). Since the primary focus of this study is the opinions of a subset of elementary school teachers in the Indanan South District of MBHTE-SULU, the descriptive method was the most suitable approach to employ.

The study used a qualitative approach as its methodology. The study's qualitative methodology was comprised of the questionnaire, which was based on the respondents' own perceptions, personal observations, and comments.

Research Locale

This study was conducted in elementary schools of Indanan South District MBHTE-SULU located at Municipality of Indanan Sulu. Among the 18 schools of Indanan South district, the researcher chooses only 10 schools to conduct this study. The targeted schools namely the following: Sapah Malaum Elementary School, Panglima Misuari Elementary School, Panglima Hajan Elementary School, Manilup Elementary School, Langpas Elementary School, Mukammali Elementary School, Población Elementary

School, Panglima Indanan Central School, Bunot Elementary School, and Dayuan Elementary School.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study were the intermediate teachers of Elementary School at Indanan South District MBHTE-SULU.

The target respondent at least 100 elementary teachers handling intermediate level. It is according to their demographic profile.

Table 1. Distribution of the Respondents according to school

INDANAN SOUHT DISTRICT	NO. OF TEACHERS
1.Sapah Malaum Elem. School	10
2.Panglima Misuari Elem. School	10
3.Panglima Hajan Elem. School	10
4.Manilup Elem. School	10
5.Mukammali Elem. School	10
6.Langpas Elem. School	10
7.Poblacion Elem. School	10
8.Pasil Elem. School	10
9.Bunot Elem. School	10
10.Dayuan Elem. School	10
TOTAL	100

Sampling Design

The researcher used the purposive sampling technique to identify and select the 100 participants from the teachers of Indanan South District Elementary School MBHTE-Sulu, all the teachers handling the intermediate level. The inclusion criteria was used in choosing the participants of the study were the following; The participants was officially teachers of Indanan South District, and have at least 5 years in service. The participants

were selected from the teachers handling the intermediate level, who monitor the behavioral tendencies of intermediate pupils.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher prepared the survey questionnaire, and asked first the permission from Dean of Graduate Studies, the school principals from the different schools in Indanan South District Elementary School, MBHTE-SULU to conduct the study. Right after the approval, the researcher disseminated the questionnaire to the respondents personally to avoid being bias during the survey. After at least 10 minutes for each respondent, the questionnaires were retrieved.

Research Instrument

The researcher used a standardize instrument adapted from the study of Precy I. Guerra (2014) about the behavioral tendencies of intermediate pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School MBHTE-SULU.

The questionnaire consisted of 2 parts. Part (1) deals with the demographic profile of the respondents which include their age, gender, educational attainment, and length of services. Part (2) consist of the elements of the behavioral problem of intermediate pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School MBHTE-SULU. their responses were categorized using the Likert's scale to make it more convenient to answer and interpret.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Both descriptive and inferential tools were employed in the treatments of data gathered for this study.

1. For research question number 1, the statistical tools used was Frequency and Percentage to determine, the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, educational attainment, and civil status.

2. For problem number 2, Standard Deviation and the weighted mean were the statistical tools used to determine the extent of behavioral tendencies of intermediate pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School, MBHTE-Sulu. Perceive by the teachers in terms of; activity level, emotional control, and aggression and destructiveness.

3. For research question number 3, T-test and One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were the statistical tools used for independent samples to determine the significant different in the extent of behavioral tendencies of intermediate pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School, MBHTE-Sulu, as perceived by the teachers in terms of; activity level, emotional control, and aggression and destructiveness; when data are grouped according to their demographic profile; age, gender, educational attainment and civil status.

4. For problem number 4, the statistical tools used was Pearson Product-Moment Correlation to determine the significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed

under Behavioral tendencies among intermediate pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School, MBHTE-Sulu.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. *What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of: Age, Gender, Educational Attainment, and Civil Status?*

1.1 In terms of Age

Table 1.1 presents the demographic profile of teacher-respondents in terms of age. It can be seen from this table that out of 100 teacher-respondents, 9 (9.0%) is from the age group of 20 years old and below, while 28 (28.0%) are 21-30 years old, and 63 (63.0%) are 31 years old and above. This study reveals that more than one-half of the total teacher-respondents involved in this study are within 31 years old and above of age brackets. This further implies that most of teacher-respondents involved in this study belong to the upper level of age group as categorized in this study.

Table 1.1 Demographic profile of teacher-respondents from Indanan South District Elementary school in terms of age.

Age	Number of respondents	Percent
20 years old and below	9	9.0%
21-30 years old	28	28.0%
31 years old and above	63	63.0%
Total	100	100%

1.2 In terms of Gender

Table 1.2 shows the demographic profile of teacher-respondents in terms of gender. It can be gleaned from this table that out of 100 teacher-respondents, 24 (24.0%) are male, and 76 (76.0%) are female. This study reveals that more than on-half of the total number of teacher-respondents involved in this study are female. This implies that great majority of the teacher-respondents from Indanan South District elementary school are predominantly female.

Table 1.2 Demographic profile of teacher-respondents from Indanan South District Elementary school in terms of gender.

Gender	Number of respondents	Percent
Male	24	24.0%
Female	76	76.0%
Total	100	100%

1.3 In terms of Educational Attainment

Table 1.3 presents the demographic profile of teacher-respondents in terms of Educational Attainment. It can be seen from this table that out of 100 teacher-respondents, 75 (75.0%) have bachelor's degree, 15 (15.0%) have bachelor's degree with Master's units, 8 (8.0%) have master's degree, and 2 (2.0%) have Doctorate degree. This study reveals that more than half of the total number of teacher-respondents have only bachelor's degree. This implies that the prevalence of bachelor's degrees among the teacher-respondents involved in this study suggest a need for an ongoing professional development and opportunities for career advancement among the elementary school teachers of Indanan South District.

Table 1.3 Demographic profile of teacher-respondents from Indanan South District Elementary school in terms of educational attainment.

Educational Attainment	Number of respondents	Percent
Bachelor's Degree	75	75.0%
Bachelor's degree with Master's units	15	15.0%
Master's degree	8	8.0%
Doctorate Degree	2	2.0%
Total	100	100%

1.4 In terms of Civil Status

Table 1.4 shows the demographic profile of teacher-respondents in terms of civil status. It can be seen from this table that out of 100 teacher-respondents, 34 (34.0%) are single, 62 (62.0%) are married, and 4 (4.0%) are either separated or widowed. This study shows that more than half of the total number of teacher-respondents are married. This result implies that Indanan South District Elementary school is pre-occupied by married elementary school teachers.

Table 1.4 Demographic profile of teacher-respondents from Indanan South District Elementary school in terms of civil status.

Civil Status	Number of respondents	Percent
Single	34	34.0%
Married	62	62.0%
Separated/Widowed	4	4.0%
Total	100	100%

2. What is the extent of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School MBHTE-Sulu, as perceived by the teachers in terms of: 2.1 Activity level, 2.2 Emotional control; and 2.3 Aggression and Destructiveness?

2.1 In the context of Activity Level

Table 2.1 shows the extent of behavioral tendencies of intermediate pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School MBHTE-Sulu as perceived by elementary teachers in the context of Activity Level. This category obtained a total weighted mean score of **3.12** with standard deviation of **1.04310** which is rated as “Lesser extent”. This result indicates that the teachers involved in this study affirmed that there is a lesser extent of behavioral tendency of elementary students among Indanan South District Elementary School. This implies that educators can prioritize reinforcing and celebrating positive behaviors within the school community. Implementing systems of recognition, such as praise, rewards, or merit-based programs, can encourage students to continue demonstrates desirable behaviors and contribute to a more positive school culture.

Notably, teacher-respondents rated the following items as “**Lesser extent**”: “Run away if not constant supervised.”, “Does not stay in seat during group sessions.”, “Constantly runs or jumps around room.”, “Fingers, feet, hands constantly in motion (tapping, drumming)”, “Requires excessive supervision and control.”, and “Out of seat without permission.”.

Table 2.1 Extent of behavioral tendencies of intermediate pupils at Indanan south district elementary school MBHTE-Sulu: Teachers’ perspective in the context of Activity Level.

Statements	Mean	S.D	Rating
1 Run away if not constant supervised.	3.29	1.387	Lesser extent
2 Does not stay in seat during group sessions.	3.30	1.202	Lesser extent
3 Constantly runs or jumps around room.	3.02	1.247	Lesser extent
4 Highly distractible, does not attend for more than a minute.	2.94	1.127	Lesser extent
5 Fingers, feet, hands constantly in motion (tapping, drumming).	3.00	1.206	Lesser extent
6 Does not stay on task unless someone is standing over him/her.	3.16	1.126	Lesser extent
7 Requires excessive supervision and control.	3.20	1.189	Lesser extent
8 Highly impulsive, has great difficulty holding back a response.	3.18	1.242	Lesser extent
9 Make inappropriate noise during class.	3.07	1.241	Lesser extent

10	Out of seat without permission.	3.07	1.148	Lesser extent
Total Weighted Mean		3.12	1.04310	Lesser extent

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00=Highest extent; (4) 3.50-4.49=Moderately extent; (3) 2.50-3.49=Lesser extent; (2) 1.50- 2.49=Least extent; (1) 1.00- 1.49=No extent at all

2.2 In the context of Emotional Control

Table 2.2 shows the extent of behavioral tendencies of intermediate pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School, MBHTE-Sulu: Teachers' perspective in the context of Emotional control. This category obtained a total weighted mean score of **2.73** with standard deviation of **1.03469** which is rated as "Lesser extent". This result indicates that the teachers involved in this study affirmed that there is a lesser extent of emotional control among elementary students at South District Elementary School. This implies that despite the lesser extent of negative emotional control, it is crucial to provide students with opportunities to learn and practice emotional regulation skills. Integrating lessons on identifying and managing emotions into the curriculum can empower students to navigate challenging situations effectively and develop healthy coping mechanisms.

Notably, teacher-respondents rated the following items, among others as "**Lesser extent**": "Severe negative reaction to criticism or correction.", "Blames own mistakes on others.", "Complains of unfairness even when equal privileges are given.", "Marked excessive mood swing for no appropriate reason." and, "Frightened and insecure in daily activities."

Table 2.2 Extent of behavioral tendencies of intermediate pupils at Indanan south district elementary school MBHTE-Sulu: Teachers' perspective in the context of behavior.

	Statements	Mean	S. D	Rating
1	Severe negative reaction to criticism or correction.	2.78	1.219	Lesser extent
2	Blames own mistakes on others.	2.74	1.116	Lesser extent
3	Tantrums if does not get own way.	2.68	1.154	Lesser extent
4	Complains of unfairness even when equal privileges are given.	2.63	1.178	Lesser extent
5	Acts suspicious on others.	2.88	1.409	Lesser extent
6	Marked excessive mood swing for no appropriate reason.	2.89	1.348	Lesser extent
7	Talks about suicide.	2.46	1.366	Least extent
8	Demand excessive praise.	2.66	1.157	Lesser extent
9	Overestimate own abilities.	2.76	1.224	Lesser extent
10	Frightened and insecure in daily activities.	2.77	1.317	Lesser extent
Total Weighted Mean		2.73	1.03469	Lesser extent

2.3 In the context of Aggression and Destructiveness

Table 2.3 shows the extent of behavioral tendencies of intermediate pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School, MBHTE-Sulu: Teachers' perspective in the context of Aggression and Destructiveness. This category obtained a total weighted mean score of 2.01 with standard deviation of 1.352 which is rated as "Moderately Agree". This result indicates a generally positive but somewhat mixed perception regarding the program's influence on behavioral aspects among the teacher-respondents. Involved in this study. Furthermore, this implies that while the preschool program has made strides in shaping certain behavioral aspects among participants, there may be room for further enhancement or refinement in specific areas.

Notably, teacher-respondents rated the following items, among others as "**Least extent**": "Engages in the self-harming behavior when she/he is frustrated. (Ex: scratching self or biting, etc.)", "Use inappropriate verbal expressions when frustrated? (Ex: yelling/ screaming, etc.)", "Automatically, cry when he/she can't answer the question or activities present.", "Uses appropriate verbal expressions when frustrated? (Ex: I need a break, or I need help)." and, "Displayed socially inappropriate behavior to gain attention from parents."

Table 2.2 Extent of behavioral tendencies of intermediate pupils at Indanan south district elementary school MBHTE-Sulu: Teachers' perspective in the context of behavior.

Statements	Mean	S. D	Rating
1 Violent temper tantrums (screaming, throwing self on floor)	2.50	1.453	Lesser extent
2 Uses objects as weapons against others.	2.59	1.371	Lesser extent
3 Aggressive to peers.	2.36	1.177	Least extent
4 Vandalism – damage public property.	2.26	1.194	Least extent
5 Interfere with other activities (blocking passage)	2.07	1.166	Least extent
6 Swear, curses, uses obscene language.	2.09	1.215	Least extent
7 Steals someone money property.	2.16	1.308	Least extent
8 Lies about situations, self, or others.	2.03	1.201	Least extent
9 Argues with teacher over behavior.	1.84	1.126	Least extent
10 Disrupts games, group activities by refusing to follow the rules.	2.01	1.352	Least extent
Total Weighted Mean	2.19	.95770	Least extent

3. Is there a significant difference in the extent of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District elementary school MBHTE-Sulu, as perceived by the teachers in terms of: Activity level, Emotional control, and Aggression and Destructiveness; when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of: 3.1 Age, 3.2 Gender; 3.3 Educational Attainment; and 3.4 Civil Status?

3.1 According to Age

Table 3.1 presents the difference in the extent of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School MBHTE-Sulu as perceived by the teachers when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of age. As shown in this table, except for Aggression and Destructiveness, all the F-values and probability values under “Activity Level” are indeed significant at alpha 0.05. This means that though elementary teacher-respondents vary in their age, generally they differ in perception towards the extent of impact of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District elementary school in the context of both Activity level and Emotional control. Meanwhile, they do not differ in their perception towards the extent of impact of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District elementary school in the context of Aggression and Destructiveness. This further implies that teacher-respondents with the age range 51 years old and above may make him/her better perceiver toward extent of impact of preschool program in the case of Indanan South District compared to those within 25 years old and below as categorized in this study, or vice versa.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable age has indeed significant intervention in the ways how teacher-respondents at Indanan South District Elementary School perceive the extent of impact of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that: “There is no significant difference in the subcategories subsumed under the extent of impact of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of age” is rejected.

Table 3.1 difference in the extent of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School MBHTE-Sulu as perceived by the teachers when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of age.

Sources of Variation		Sum of squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Activity Level	Between Groups	16.264	2	8.132	8.625	.000	Significant
	Within Groups	91.453	97	.943			
	Total	107.717	99				
Emotional control	Between Groups	21.473	2	10.737	12.323	.000	Significant
		84.514	97	.871			

Aggression and Destructiveness	Within Groups Total	105.988	99				
	Between Groups	1.923	2	.962	1.049	.354	Not Significant
	Within Groups Total	88.879	97	.916			
	Between Groups	90.802	99				
	Within Groups Total						
	Between Groups						

* Significant at alpha 0.05

A Post Hoc Analysis using Tukey test was conducted to identify which among groups classified according to age have different levels of mean in the extent of impact of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District Elementary as perceived by teachers when data are grouped according to respondents' demographic profile in terms of age.

On Activity Level: It shows that teacher-respondents who are from lower age group of 20 years old and below as categorized in this study obtained the mean difference of 1.49246* and 1.34603* with Standard Error of .37206 and .34601 and p-value of .000 and .001 which is both significant at alpha 0.05 over those teacher-respondents who are from the middle and upper age group of 21-30 years old and 31 and above years old, respectively. This indicates that teacher-respondents from lower age group are better perceiver on the extent of impact of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District elementary in the context of activity level compared to those respondents involved in this study from middle and upper age group.

On Emotional control: It shows that teacher-respondents who are from lower age group of 20 years old and below as categorized in this study obtained the mean difference of 1.76190* and 1.45238* with Standard Error of .35767 and .33262 and p-value of .000 and .000 which is both significant at alpha 0.05 over those teacher-respondents who are from the middle and upper age group of 21-30 years old and 31 and above years old, respectively. This indicates that teacher-respondents from lower age group are better perceiver on the extent of impact of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School in the context of emotional control compared to those respondents involved in this study from middle and upper age group.

Table 3.1.1 Post Hoc Analysis: Differences in the extent of impact of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District elementary as perceived by teachers when data are grouped according to age.

Dependent Variable	(I) Grouping Year Level	by	(J) Grouping Year Level	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Activity Level	20 years old and below		21-30 years old	1.49246*	.37206	.000
			31 years old and above	1.34603*	.34601	.001

Emotional control	20 years old and below	21-30 years old	1.76190*	.35767	.000
		31 years old and above	1.45238*	.33262	.000

3.2 According to Gender

Table 3.2 presents the difference in the extent of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School, MBHTE-Sulu as perceived by the teachers when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of gender. As shown in this table, except for Aggression and Destructiveness, all the F-values and probability values under “Emotional control” are indeed significant at alpha 0.05. This means that, male and female teacher-respondents involved in this study differ in their perception towards the extent of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School, MBHTE-Sulu. This further implies that being male student-respondent may make him a better perceiver toward the extent of impact of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School, or vice versa.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable gender has indeed significant intervention in the ways how teacher-respondents at Indanan South District Elementary School perceive the extent of impact of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District elementary school. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that: “There is no significant difference in the subcategories subsumed under the extent of impact of Behavioral

Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District elementary school when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of gender” is rejected.

Table 3.2 Difference in the extent of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District elementary school MBHTE-Sulu as perceived by the teachers when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms gender.

Variables	Grouping	Mean	S.D	Mean Difference	t	Sig.	Description
Activity Level	Male	3.8000	.85262	.89079	3.900	.000	Significant
	Female	2.9092	1.01011				
Emotional control	Male	3.2958	.94615	.75110	3.246	.002	Significant
	Female	2.5447	1.00072				
Aggression and	Male	2.1833	.73819	-.01009	-.045		Not Significant

Destructiveness	Female	2.193	1.0215	.96
s		4	5	4

* Significant at alpha 0.05

3.3 According to Educational Attainment

Table 3.3 presents the difference in the extent of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School, MBHTE-Sulu as perceived by the teachers when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of educational attainment. It can be gleaned from this table that all the F-values and probability values of the subcategories subsumed under the extent of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School, MBHTE-Sulu as perceived by the teachers are not significant at alpha 0.05. This means that though the teacher-respondents involved in this study vary in their educational attainment, generally they do not differ in their perceptions toward the extent of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School. It implies that teacher-respondents with doctorate degree may not be a better perceiver on the extent of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School compared to those who only have bachelor's degree, and vice versa.

Hence, it is safe to say that the educational attainment variable has no significant intervention in the ways how preschool teacher-respondents perceive the extent of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that: "There is no significant difference in the subcategories subsumed under the extent of impact of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of educational attainment" is accepted.

Table 3.4 Difference in the extent of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District elementary school MBHTE-Sulu as perceived by the teachers when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of Educational Attainment.

Sources of Variation		Sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Activity Level	Between Groups	.557	3	.186	.166	.919	Not Significant
	Within Groups	107.160	96	1.116			
	Total	107.717	99				
Emotional control	Between Groups	.509	3	.170	.154	.927	Not Significant
	Within Groups	105.479	96	1.099			
	Total	105.988	99				
Aggression and Destructiveness	Between Groups	1.649	3	.550	.592	.622	Not Significant
	Within Groups	89.153	96	.929			

Within Groups Total 90.802 99

* Significant at alpha 0.05

3.4 According to Civil status

Table 3.4 presents the difference in the extent of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School, MBHTE-Sulu as perceived by the teachers when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of civil status. It can be gleaned from this table that all the F-values and probability values of the subcategories subsumed are not significant at alpha 0.05. This means that though the teacher-respondents involved in this study vary in civil status, generally they do not differ in their perceptions toward the extent of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School. It implies that married teacher-respondents may not be a better perceiver on the extent of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School compared to those who are single, and vice versa.

Hence, it is safe to say that the civil status variable has no significant intervention in the ways how preschool teacher-respondents perceive the extent of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District elementary school as perceived by teachers. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that: “There is no significant difference in the subcategories subsumed under the extent of impact of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District elementary school when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of civil status” is accepted.

Table 3.4 Difference in the extent of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District elementary school MBHTE-Sulu as perceived by the teachers when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of civil status.

Sources of Variation		Sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Activity Level	Between Groups	4.470	2	2.235	2.100	.128	Not Significant
	Within Groups	103.247	97	1.064			
	Total	107.717	99				
Emotional control	Between Groups	2.874	2	1.437	1.352	.264	Not Significant
	Within Groups	103.114	97	1.063			
	Total	105.988	99				
Aggression and Destructiveness	Between Groups	.719	2	.360	.387	.680	Not Significant
	Within Groups	90.083	97	.929			
	Total	90.802	99				

4. Is there a significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under Behavioral Tendencies among Intermediate pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School MBHTE-Sulu?

Table 4 shows the correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School as perceived by teachers. As shown in the table, the computed Pearson correlation Coefficients (Pearson r) between these variables are significant at alpha 0.05.

Furthermore, the correlational degree among the extent of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School as perceived by teachers is as follows:

- 1) Very High positive degree of correlation among the extent of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School as perceived by teachers between the context of Activity Level and Emotional control. This implies that promoting higher levels of activity in the classroom may positively influence students' emotional control. Educators should consider incorporating engaging and interactive learning activities to stimulate activity levels while also providing opportunities for students to develop and practice emotional regulation skills.
- 2) High positive degree of correlation among the extent of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School as perceived by teachers between the context of Activity Level and Aggression and Destructiveness. This implies that higher activity levels may potentially contribute to increased levels of aggression and destructiveness in students. Educators should be mindful of providing appropriate outlets for energy and promoting positive outlets for expression, such as physical activity breaks, creative outlets, or structured play.
- 3) High positive degree of correlation among the extent of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School as perceived by teachers between the context of Emotional control and Aggression and Destructiveness. This implies that students with lower levels of emotional control may be more prone to exhibiting aggressive or destructive behaviors. Educators should prioritize interventions aimed at promoting emotional regulation skills and providing support for students to manage and express their emotions in healthy ways.

Hence, it is safe to say that generally the Activity Level and behavior are highly correlated. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that "There is no the significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the extent of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School as perceived by teachers" is rejected.

Table 4 shows the correlation among the subcategories subsumed under the extent of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School as perceived by teachers.

Variables		Pearson	Sig.	N	Description
Dependent	Independent	r			
Activity Level	Emotional control	.827**	.000	100	Very High
	Aggression and Destructiveness	.611**	.000	100	High
Emotional control	Aggression and Destructiveness	.684**	.000	100	High

*Correlation coefficient is significant at alpha .05

Correlation Coefficient Scales Adopted from Hopkins, Will (2002):

0.0-0.1 = Nearly Zero; 0.1-0.3 = Low; 0.3-0.5 = Moderate; 0.5-0.7 = High; 0.7-0.9 = Very High; 0.9-1 = Nearly Perfect.

Conclusions

The study concludes the following:

1) The demographic profile of teacher-respondents in Indanan South District is characterized by a predominance of females. Additionally, a substantial majority falls within the age group of 31 years old and above of age brackets. Furthermore, majority of teacher-respondents are married and hold bachelor's degree. These findings provide valuable insights into the composition of teaching personnel in the district. It can be concluded that there is a need to form a strategy for teachers' professional development, and resource allocation to better meet the needs both the teachers and students at Indanan South District Elementary School.

2) Across all sub-categories assessed, activity level, emotional control, and aggression and destructiveness, teacher-respondents consistently rated these behavioral tendencies having "less extent." This consensus is reflected in the total weighted mean scores of 3.12, 2.73, and 2.01 for activity level, emotional control, and aggression and destructiveness, respectively. The accompanying standard deviations of 1.04310, 1.03469, and 1.352 suggest a degree of variability in perceptions among teacher-respondents but overall reinforce the notion of these behavioral tendencies being less extent within the intermediate pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School. These findings conclude the importance of addressing behavioral challenges and implementing targeted interventions to support the socio-emotional development of intermediate pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School.

3) Generally, the differing perceptions of teacher-respondents based on age and gender imply that these demographic factors may influence how behavioral tendencies are

observed and interpreted in the classroom. Understanding these nuances is crucial for educators to effectively support students in their behavioral development and create inclusive learning environments that cater to their unique needs.

4) Subcategories subsumed under the extent of Behavioral Tendencies of Intermediate Pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School have a high positive correlation implying a strong interdependency among subcategories subsumed. This correlation suggests that the various aspects of behavioral tendencies, as observed and perceived by teachers, are closely related and tend to align with one another.

Recommendations

This study recommends the following:

1) DepEd administrators should ensure access to support services such as counseling, special education, and health and nutrition programs to address the diverse needs of intermediate pupils at Indanan South District Elementary School and promote their holistic development.

2) Teachers at the Indanan South District Elementary School may prioritize their own professional development and growth to stay abreast of current research, best practices, and emerging trends in education. Engaging in ongoing training, workshops, and professional learning sessions focusing on behavior management strategies. Teachers may not get tired of knowing and exploring ways that will help them reduce the behavioral problem.

3) Educators are encouraged to adopt a holistic approach to behavior assessment, considering multiple dimensions such as social, emotional, and academic behaviors. Implement frameworks or tools that facilitate comprehensive behavior assessment, allowing educators to capture the interconnected nature of student behavior more accurately.

4) Moreover, future researchers in the field of education are encouraged to conduct study like this one to further assess the behavioral tendency of intermediate pupils and how this will impact their academic performance, socio-emotional development, and overall well-being.

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Compliance with Ethical Standards

First and foremost, each participant received a detailed informed consent form outlining the trial's objectives, procedures, possible risks and benefits, and confidentiality policies. In addition, all trial data points were meticulously anonymized when the respondents' personal information had no bearing on the trial's outcomes. Data collection was carried out in a private setting to protect participant privacy, and the collected data was stored in a secure archive that was only accessible by the researchers. All participants were treated with respect, regardless of differences in opinions and points of view.

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